

Human Exposure to Micro- and Nanoplastics

Executive Summary

Embedded within the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, the PlasticsFatE (Plastics Fate and Effects in the Human Body) project (April 2021 – March 2025) aims to deepen our understanding of how micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) and their additives and associated contaminants affect human health. This Policy Brief outlines key insights from the PlasticsFatE project on the primary human exposure pathways to MNPs (ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact), and the urgent need for further research and regulatory action to mitigate associated risks.

Background

Research by Luo et al. (2022), Monikh et al. (2022), Kokalj et al. (2023), Ramsperger et al. (2023), Schwartz et al. (2023), and Wieland et al. (2024) highlights how MNPs enter the environment and explores how embedded organisms come into contact with MNPs given their specific exposure routes.

Given the rising presence of MNPs in the environment, understanding the human exposure to MNPs is critical. MNPs have been described in various human tissues and organs e.g., lung, placenta, liver, spleen, kidney, brain and blood (for an overview see Ramsperger et al. (2023), and Nihart et al. (2025)). MNPs may cause cellular stress and inflammation and raise concerns about long-term health effects.

This research is essential not only for assessing acute risks but also for informing future regulations and improving safety measures in response to chronic MNP exposure. As there are still large gaps in our knowledge of the hazard potential of MNPs, reducing releases and exposure are the most important precautionary measures to minimize the risk potential of this complex class of environmental pollutants.

The studies conducted in PlasticsFatE provide a nuanced understanding of the multifaceted exposure to MNPs. The following key insights have emerged:

Exposure

MNPs are either deliberately manufactured (primary MNPs) or they result from the fragmentation or breakdown of macroplastics during the use phase of plastic-containing products, after release into the environment or after disposal (secondary MNPs). In addition to mass applications with high release rates, such as for tyre rubber or textiles, the improper disposal of plastics also contributes to MNP pollution in diverse environmental media, including soil, water, and air. Released particles undergo environmental transformations that affect their morphology (e.g. roughness), surface properties (e.g. coatings with functional groups and surface charge alterations), and interaction with organisms and cells (Ramsperger et al., 2020; Wieland et al., 2024; Witzmann et al., 2022). Differences in environmental conditions, such as saltwater versus freshwater exposure, determine the extent to which MNPs are internalized and processed in an organism or in cells, influencing their toxicity (Luo et al., 2022; Monikh et al., 2022). Humans are exposed to MNPs through various routes, via ingestion, inhalation, and via dermal contact with environmental media, e.g. contaminated water, with personal care products and synthetic clothes being the most prominent sources for dermal exposure.

Ingestion

Dietary intake is a major route of MNP exposure, stemming from contaminated food and drinking water. Commercial seafood such as mussels and fish from contaminated water bodies contribute to human exposure (Kumar et al., 2021). But plants can also absorb MNP from soils. Crops like wheat and lettuce absorb MNPs from soils polluted by agricultural practices (e.g., mulching foils, sewage sludge) or plastic waste. In this way, MNPs can migrate from soils into food webs. Absorbed particles predominantly accumulate in plant roots, with minimal translocation to shoots (<3%) (Luo et al., 2022; Zantis, 2024). Further along the food chain, MNPs may transfer from plants to invertebrates like insects and snails, and subsequently to vertebrates at higher trophic levels, such as fish. Whether they also reach humans via farm animals in the food chain remains a task for future research (Aardema et al. 2024, Pause et al. 2024). While the biomagnification of MNPs across trophic levels remains debated, their accumulation within organisms is considered plausible, with some studies reporting converging findings (Akhbarizadeh et al., 2019; Ramsperger et al., 2023; Schwartz et al., 2023).

Inhalation

Airborne MNPs pose a significant risk, especially in indoor environments, where concentrations are notably higher than outdoors due to synthetic materials like carpets and textiles. MNP in the size of less than 10µm can be inhaled, contributing to human exposure through respiratory pathways (Kokalj et al., 2023).

Dermal Contact

Direct exposure of the skin to MNPs can be caused in particular by the use of personal care products (PCPs) containing MNP or the wearing of clothing made of synthetic fibres. While MNPs are still permitted in PCPs in other countries, in the EU the manufacture of products with intentionally added MNPs is now restricted. But due to long transition periods provided for this regulation (e.g., until 2035 for make-up), MNPs are still present in some PCPs in the EU. However, translocation through the healthy skin is considered unlikely. Instead, ingestion and inhalation remain the primary routes of exposure from PCPs (Ramsperger et al., 2022, 2023).

Summary

Human exposure to MNPs is multifaceted, arising from ingestion (contaminated food and beverages), inhalation (airborne particles), and dermal contact (PCPs and synthetic clothes). These pathways highlight the pervasive nature of MNPs in ecosystems and their potential to be transferred within food chains (Monikh et al. 2022; Ramsperger et al., 2023), increasing exposure risks to humans via agricultural and aquatic sources. The variability in how MNPs are internalized underscores the need for further research to understand the underlying mechanisms and their health implications, and to inform mitigation strategies (Ramsperger et al., 2023; Monikh et al., 2022).

Further Research Needed

Further research into human exposure to MNP is essential to fully understand the scope of human risk. While we know that MNPs are present in food, air, and water, there is limited data on the long-term health effects of chronic exposure, especially through ingestion and inhalation. Indoor air in particular plays a special role here due to the long daily exposure time and the presumably higher MNP concentrations compared to outdoor air (Ramsperger 2023, Wieland et al. 2022). Yet more studies are needed to quantify these exposure levels and sources, and to evaluate the risks of long-term inhalation. This should lead to the recommendation of risk management measures.

Additionally, the dynamics of MNPs within food chains require further exploration, particularly in crops and seafood, to understand how these particles accumulate and transfer through ecosystems into human diets. Variability in environmental conditions, such as the differences between saltwater and freshwater exposure, also plays a crucial role in MNP behaviour, influencing how they are absorbed and processed by organisms. Investigating these environmental factors will refine our understanding of exposure levels and critical pathways across different settings.

Moreover, there is an urgent need for standardized detection methods, especially for smaller MP and NP, to better measure MNPs in food, air, and water, as well as human tissues and body fluids (e.g. urine, blood). Accurate and comparable detection is key to obtaining reliable data on exposure levels and developing effective risk assessments. Expanding research in these areas will not only deepen our understanding of how humans are exposed to MNPs but also helps to shape more informed regulations and safety standards (e.g. for occupational exposure limits for MNP in air).

Implications for EU and National Policy: Blind Spots and Recommendations

The implications of MNP exposure for EU and national policy reveal several blind spots and regulatory requirements that need urgent attention. Current regulations, particularly in the areas of food safety and air quality, do not adequately account for the pervasive presence of MNPs in the environment and the potential risks they pose to human health. Despite growing evidence of MNP contamination in food, water, and air, there are no comprehensive policies in place to monitor or limit exposure, leaving significant gaps in protective measures and mitigation actions.

As a result of the work in PlasticsFatE, the following points highlight critical blind spots and recommendations for policy development:

- Advance research on MNP biomagnification in food chains that are important for humans
- Promote standardized measurement and testing methods across the EU to ensure consistency, comparability, and accuracy in detecting MNPs and their effects, supported by rigorous quality control/quality assurance (QC/QA) measures such as method validation, interlaboratory comparisons, and contamination control
- Develop a list of MNP-specific biomarkers in human samples (blood, urine) to assess human exposure and effects in particular at workplaces, where the exposure can be enhanced
- Officially recognize MNPs as a new class of emerging chemical pollutants
- Establish clear regulatory limits for MNPs in food, water, and air
- Expand indoor air quality standards to address the concentration of MNPs in homes, workplaces, and public spaces
- Implement comprehensive monitoring systems to track MNP levels in (agricultural) soils, surface- and groundwater bodies, crops, seafood, and processed foods
- Define maximum allowable concentrations of MNPs in reclaimed water used for irrigation, based on current scientific knowledge and risk assessments (EU Regulation 2020/741) – these thresholds should be regularly reviewed and updated as new research becomes available
- Support the development of strategies to reduce the emission of persistent polymer particles during the life cycle of products

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